

Integrating, Processing and Presenting Big Geodata with Earth Observation Datacubes in an Interdisciplinary Research Context

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Abstract

The heterogeneous background of stakeholders in application-oriented research projects often entails the need to combine diverse data sources for processing and to present the results to an audience with varying technical affinity. In geodata-based contexts, datacubes have proven to be a powerful integration and analysis tool, so paired with adequate visualisation, they carry high potential to address this task. In the context of a project on remote sensing in agricultural crop production, we combined several pieces of free and open-source geo software to create an architecture centered around an instance of the Open Data Cube (ODC) framework that utilises purpose-built web applications and services to minimise the gap between data providers and information consumers.

1. Introduction

Application-oriented research projects often involve diverse consortium members, from universities to research institutions, from authorities to domain end users. This requires the integration of very heterogeneous data sources from very heterogeneous providers, the facilitation of their combined processing, and the presentation of the results in adequate ways. The challenge here is not only the technical realisation itself, but possibly even more the design of solutions that cater to this wide user group, balancing feature-richness with easy usability. Data is abundant, and processing power plentiful, but it all needs to go the last mile to the final user.

For application domains that are based on spatio-temporal data, such as in the environmental context, *datacubes* have proven to be an effective tool for gathering big amounts of such data and making it available for efficient large-scale analysis (e.g. Chatenoux et al., 2021). The key achievement of this concept is to free domain experts from the burden of having to manage all that data on a low level – instead, they are supplied with a high-level tool that provides all the features they need, letting them focus on the actual domain task (Wang et al., 2022).

One such interdisciplinary, geodata-based research project is “AgriSens DEMMIN 4.0”, which aims to advance remote sensing for the digitalisation in agricultural crop production. Thus, the user group is quite diverse with a vast range of technical backgrounds, including programmers, domain scientists such as agronomists, as well as farmers and agricultural advisors. Evidently, Earth observation (EO) data from satellites or drones is the key resource being leveraged in the project – so far, agriculture is not yet taking advantage of EO products widely,

with imaged area being far below 10% in many European countries (Pavlenko et al., 2023). Therefore, the project not only addresses the creation of novel remote-sensing-based application techniques and their implementation, but puts an equally distinct emphasis on the development of an accompanying data integration and visualisation system that aims at bringing the wealth of data to those that are supposed to eventually benefit from it.

In this paper, we describe how we combine several pieces of free and open-source geo software to create an architecture that addresses this complex task. The following text explains the capabilities of each chosen system component and how they helped us to close the gap between remote sensing data providers and information consumers in agricultural crop production by facilitating necessary analysis steps and feeding the results into adequate presentation tools for decision makers. Figure 1 schematically summarises the system architecture and may be a good reference to come back to every now and then while reading through the paper.

2. Methods and Results

2.1 General architecture

In our IT architecture, we utilise one central datacube to conquer this problem, which acts as a cloud-based geospatial data holding and computation platform with some visualisation capabilities. It gathers a multitude of data, ranging from optical and radar raster imagery through weather data to in-situ field measurements. These are acquired from standard sources or supplied by project partners and pre-processed into an interoperable, analysis-ready state. These resources can then be accessed through APIs for external usage, or computations can be carried out directly on the datacube and the results immediately displayed with tools hosted on the same server.

Figure 1: Schema of the system architecture.

2.2 Hardware framework

The system consists of 80 CPU cores and 1.42 TB memory as a virtual machine hosted on the “Compute Cloud” of the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities (LRZ), which is physically located in Garching near Munich, Germany. Apart from utilising the computing resources available there, this location also opens up synergies with existing projects: We can make use of the enormous amount of EO data that is already available within the LRZ’s “Data Science Storage” (DSS) as well as the “terabyte” platform (Albrecht, Eberle and Schwinger, 2022) that LRZ operates together with the German Aerospace Center (DLR). These storages are directly mounted into our server, allowing the datacube very fast access to petabytes of imagery without having to duplicate it again. This saves not only efforts and costs, but also emissions, a topic that is receiving increasing attention (e.g. Wilkinson et al., 2024).

2.3 Software framework

Hosted on an *Ubuntu* server, the technical system consists of individual *Docker* containers which are orchestrated via *Docker Compose*. Web access by users is through a *Caddy* web server which reverse-proxies all requests to their respective targets. If desired, fine-grained access restriction can be added by including an *Authentik*-powered auth layer, providing a convenient single-sign-on solution through the *OAuth* protocol. Monitoring is done with *Portainer* and *Prometheus* linked to a dedicated *Grafana* dashboard.

The core of our thematic infrastructure is an instance of the *Open Data Cube* (ODC) framework (Killough, 2018). Its backbone is a *PostgreSQL* database into which datasets are ingested by registering their metadata fields (like spatio-temporal extent, reference system, raster shape etc.) and links to the location of the individual assets. The further components will be explained later, after first addressing which data is being dealt with in the project context.

2.4 Data types and formats

The pre-available data from the “terabyte” project includes a wide range of common EO satellite imagery from the various Landsat and Sentinel missions, but also MODIS and VIIRS, as well as processed products like various digital elevation models (DEMs). Notably, all Sentinel-2 Level-2A Collection-1 data over Europe from 2018 onwards is available, which is the main optical data we work with. Likewise, for the colleagues working with radar, Sentinel-1 GRD data is broadly available and an NRB product for a small but increasing extent. Ingestion is ongoing; the total storage volume across all datasets currently amounts to 50 petabytes (DLR, 2024). As we are only secondary users of this data, we do not have influence on how it is supplied, so must use it in the given format. For the Sentinel-2 data, this is the original JPEG-2000 format. If needed data is not in the catalogue (yet), we resort to procuring it from the *Registry of Open Data on AWS* (Amazon, 2024).

All raster data that we create ourselves, however, is stored in the Cloud-Optimised GeoTIFF (COG) format, allowing for efficient sub-tile access, even from remote machines over the internet (Leith et al., 2024). This is particularly important as in the context of agriculture often only data for a specific field is needed, i.e. a few hectares to a few square kilometers of area, but access is desired quickly on-demand. Self-created data includes calculated products such as plant vitality anomaly (Friedrich, Löw et al., 2024) or InSAR coherence (Ullmann et al., 2019). These are usually produced with Python scripts, leveraging libraries like *rasterio* (Gillies et al., 2013).

Additionally, project partners contribute self-created products such as raster output of biomass and leaf area index (LAI) models. These are also required to be supplied in COG format. Additionally, they must be accompanied by metadata in the YAML format that is required for ingestion into the ODC – to help create this, a template is provided by datacube staff to project partners and one-on-one help given where needed. The transfer of the actual data is done via a *Nextcloud* instance hosted on the datacube server, which combines the positive aspect of

being a familiar graphical user interface (GUI) for uploaders with the convenience of being easy to set up for admins and directly writing into the server’s file system, minimising the time spent copying files around manually.

Some data from institutional providers, such as observations and interpolations routinely created by the German Weather Service (DWD), has to be accepted in the form it is given, e.g. via SFTP. For these, Python scripts have been developed that automatise the download, conversion and ingestion as far as possible, being run semi-autonomously as e.g. monthly cron jobs.

Another source of remotely sensed imagery in the project context are drones. After flying, partners usually process their data themselves, resulting in orthorectified and georeferenced mosaics in GeoTIFF format. Some of these have been transferred to the datacube in the same fashion as explained above for self-calculated products. Prospectively, we would like to move this workflow to the cloud too, utilising e.g. OpenDroneMap (OpenDroneMap authors, 2020).

Lastly, field campaigns and permanently installed sensor systems yield in-situ measurement data. As a different project partner already had an established platform to store these, so far they were not incorporated into the datacube systemically, but only on a case-by-case basis by the respective scientist who needed them.

Figure 2: Data sources in the AgriSens DEMMIN 4.0 project.

Satellite imagery from data providers (e.g. ESA) is made available in DSS or terrabyte. If unavailable there, it is sourced from a third-party host (e.g. AWS). Project partners create drone-based remote sensing imagery, sensors supply continuous observations, and farmers and researchers gather in-situ data when visiting the field for treatment or on-site research. Some of this data is pre-processed by the partners themselves before supplying it to the project datacube.

2.5 Data exploration

For human exploration of available products, a GUI is provided by the web application *ODC Explorer* (Hooke et al., 2024), which is hosted on our server. It offers click-based navigation through a timeline and a map view, allowing users to discover the various products and their spatio-temporal coverage from an aggregated overview down to the individual asset level. All metadata can be listed if desired.

For machine-readable communication, this same tool also offers an API endpoint that exposes the same metadata according to the emergent STAC standard (STAC API Contributors, 2023). This API can of course also be consumed in any STAC-compliant client, e.g. the popular *STAC Browser* web application (Mohr et al., 2024).

2.6 Scientific computation

Our main interface for scientific computation is *Jupyter Hub*, (Project Jupyter, 2024a), a multi-user server for *Jupyter notebooks*, which are a popular form of organising code and its output in the data science world. For each user, authenticated through the *Authentik* layer, a dedicated *Jupyter Lab* (Project Jupyter, 2024b) instance is spawned in its own *Docker* container. It can access all previously mentioned data and has a certain amount of computing resources allocated to it, including ample personal storage for results. Users are provided with a web-based integrated development environment (IDE) in which they can develop, execute and debug code in Python or R, arguably the most popular programming languages in the EO community. Both offer straightforward packages for connecting to an ODC, namely *datacube* (ODC Development Team, 2024) and *odcR* (Schwalb-Willmann, 2022). These and other often-used packages and libraries (like *GDAL*, *numpy*, *xarray*, *rasterio*, *terra*, etc.) are already pre-installed. With this tool, scientists receive a state-of-the-art analysis environment in which they can work closely to the data and use all the powers of full-fledged programming languages and their extensive EO-friendly ecosystems.

Another option to work with the data is via *openEO*, the new simple and unified way to interact with big EO data cloud processing backends (Schramm, Pebesma et al., 2021). We incorporate this emerging standard by utilising the *openEO Spring Driver* (Jacob, Claus et al., 2023), an adapter to translate user-submitted openEO requests into ODC-based environments. The support in our ODC environment is experimental but promising.

2.7 Interoperability

For compatibility with legacy software, it is also possible to request rendered images of pre-configured analysis algorithms via a conventional *Web Map Service* (WMS) (Open Geospatial Consortium, 2006). These are served by an instance of the powerful *datacube-ows* package (Haesler et al., 2024). It works off a configuration file that defines available layers by specifying which bands of which ODC products are needed and should be combined in which way. Upon being queried with a WMS *GetMap* request, the package then automatically retrieves the needed data, processes it accordingly and serves the rendered PNG image back to the client. The offered styling API (ODC Steering Council, 2024) is quite potent: It provides possibilities for linear or non-linear band math, including pre-configured function templates like normalised difference, and allows for easy scaling and colour mapping, including transparency capabilities. For the colour ramps, users can directly use those known from *matplotlib* (Hunter, 2007) or freely define their own, as well as style the legend to be served with the accompanying *GetLegendGraphic* request.

The configuration is principally expressed in JSON format, but can be extended with Python code to dynamically create more complex configurations and especially to define computation rules for layers. These “index functions” are called with the automatically-retrieved data and can modify this *xarray* as needed, from simple band math to more complex operations, before *datacube-ows* takes care of the rest again. However, common tasks like masking do not need to be done this way as options for this are also already included in the styling API. Within our project, this tool is mainly used to calculate and serve croptype-specific plant vitality anomaly products based on

vegetation indices, the configuration for which can be inspected at the respective repository of our GitHub organisation (Friedrich, 2024a). The service is used by farmers and agricultural advisors directly in QGIS (QGIS Foundation, 2023), as well as through the *All My Fields* web application and within the *FieldMApp* mobile application (see below).

2.8 Simple GUIs for non-technical experts

The components showcased so far are all rather technical. The final goal, however, is to connect farmers and other end users to the analysis results – persons who often cannot or do not want to deal with complex interfaces. These tools, albeit valuable for their specific user group, are therefore not sufficient overall, so need to be complemented by others that feature easy-to-use graphical interfaces. Drawing on the possibilities of modern web technologies, we realise these through purpose-built web apps.

For example, first tests revealed that accessing the plant vitality anomaly layers via WMS in QGIS is bothersome. As the anomaly is croptype-specific, there is one layer for winter wheat, one for maize, one for potatoes, etc. If a farmer has multiple fields with differing crops, which is almost always the case, they had to check different layers for each of their fields. To ease this task, we created a web application with an OpenLayers-powered map component (Hocevar, Schaub et al., 2024) that accepts field geometries with croptype information as a GeoJSON file (Butler et al., 2016) via drag&drop. It then zooms to the file’s extent and loads the corresponding WMS layer for each polygon encountered in the GeoJSON, masking it to the outline of the field boundary. Temporal navigation is possible via a simple time slider. This application is very basic, yet it makes the data significantly more accessible. As it is a rather static asset, the needed GeoJSON can be created by trained agricultural advisors for their clients, further reducing the barriers for farmers to take advantage of additional information for their treatment decisions.

Figure 3. User interface of the prototype of the “All My Fields” web application: OpenLayers web map, displaying WMS layers served by datacube-ows, masked by GeoJSON polygons, with an OpenStreetMap basemap and an HTML5 time slider.

In a similar fashion, a basic demonstrator has been developed for showcasing the output of a water balance model for irrigated potato fields – the main difference being that in this case the data is not requested pre-rendered via WMS, but as COGs that are rendered directly in the browser, again using OpenLayers.

A different project partner develops a mobile application named “FieldMApp”, which is used by farmers both in the field as well as in the office to digitise and monitor areas of lower yield within crop fields (Friedrich, Löw et al., 2024). Certainly, this tool also makes use of the plant vitality anomaly products. As the application is developed with the platform-agnostic *Flutter* framework whose standard mapping component *flutter_map* (Ryan et al., 2024) does not yet support COGs, it was necessary to resort to WMS for serving the raster data. As mentioned above, this is comfortably possible by configuring *datacube-ows* on top of ODC. However, for detailed reports on individual areas of lower yield, raw data is needed on FieldMApp servers, which the datacube provides as COGs via the STAC endpoint.

Another – surprisingly simple – feature request was put forward by agronomists that regularly use satellite imagery for field treatment planning. Despite the existence of portals like Sentinel Hub’s *EO Browser* (Sinergise, 2024) that seem to make the discovery and download of EO data quite easy, they reported to often be spending hours of working time just gathering the data they need. As a response, we developed a simple web service for querying Sentinel-2 data for a custom bounding box and time span which can then be downloaded as a single ZIP file. The frontend is shown in Figure 4: It allows the user to specify a spatial and a temporal extent as well as a selection of desired bands and vegetation indices (NDVI, EVI, etc.) and a filename pattern. When clicking “check search”, the backend reports how many scenes were found for the given extent – if the user is happy with that, they can initiate the actual processing. For all scenes in the specified time interval, the backend will then gather all bands that have been explicitly requested or are implicitly needed for the index calculation, clip them to exactly the supplied bounding box and apply the index formulas, before compressing everything into an archive and offering it for download. The source code is publicly available on GitHub (Friedrich, 2024b). Despite the very rudimentary implementation, the agronomists reported successful usage of the service and are now using it on a somewhat regular basis, finding it a time-saving asset in their toolbox. When further work towards the stability of the backend has been done, especially regarding the queuing of several jobs and status updates about their progress to the user, it might even be included as a regular resource in their QGIS training courses.

Figure 4: A very simple GUI for downloading satellite imagery.

3. Conclusion

Overall, the challenge of interoperating various data supplies, processing chains and custom-tailored interfaces – as typically encountered in interdisciplinary research projects – requires complex solutions, but can be achieved quite well by utilising a datacube approach with free and open source geo software building blocks. Our integrated system successfully demonstrates such a use case for the domain of remote sensing in agriculture.

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